

UNDERSTANDING PAIN SENSITIVITY IN INDIVIDUALS WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

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Introduction

Over the past decades, there is a plethora of paper publications on pain sensitivity of individuals with intellectual as well as developmental disabilities. However, literature investigating pain sensitivity of individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is too sparse. In fact, according to Bursch et al. (2004), pain experts often fail to recognize signs and symptoms of pain suffered by individuals with ASD. Hence, it is clinically important to take note of findings from medical records, parental interviews and reports based on the cross-battery psycho-educational assessment that provide information on any form of pain exacerbated by sensory processing abnormalities and/or persistent arousal that characterize individuals with ASD (see also Courchesne et al., 1989; Hutt et al., 1965).

A few hypotheses/theories have been put forward to explain the apparent pain insensitivity of individuals with ASD. For example, there is the Stereotyped Behavior Hypothesis. According to this hypothesis, it is believed that certain repetitive actions (e.g., rocking oneself or flapping of arms or hands) cause an increased release of endorphins, leading to a reduction of pain sensation. This may explain why individuals with ASD often fail to report of pain or feeling little or no pain at all when they meet with physical accidents (Nutrition Health Review, 2006).

Another example is the Opioid Excess Theory. It postulates that ASD is caused by a metabolic disorder in which opioid peptides produced through metabolism of gluten and casein pass through an abnormally permeable intestinal membrane, and then proceed to exert an effect on neurotransmission through binding with opioid receptors (Millward et al., 2008). The theory has suggested that excessive brain opioid activity results in pain insensitivity in individuals with ASD and also contributes to the pathogenesis of ASD (Frescka & Davis, 1991; Gillberg, 1995; Panksepp, 1979). According to Allely (2012), “[T]he hyperfunction of the endogenous opioid system may actually explain, if not all, of the symptoms associated with ASD including (i) reduced socialization and aloofness; (ii) reduced clinging in animals; (iii) diminished crying; (iv) repetitive stereotyped behaviors; (v) promotion of convulsive activity; (vi) insensitivity to pain; (vii) episodes of motor hyperactivity alternating with hypoactivity; and (viii) affective lability” (p.2).

In one interesting study done in Japan on the relationship between opioid hormone and ASD, Naganitsu et al. (1997) mea-

sured cerebral-spinal fluid (CSF) levels of beta-endorphin (an opioid hormone) in 19 Japanese preschoolers, aged 2-6 years old, with typical ASD. Their findings failed to find any significant correlation between CSF levels and clinical symptoms, which included self-injurious behavior, pain insensitivity and stereotyped movement. However, CSF beta-endorphin levels were reported to be significantly higher in children with Rett Syndrome. The findings from the Japanese study indicated that neurons containing beta-endorphin might not be involved in children with infantile autism. This, in turn, means that no relationship between the dysfunction of brain opioid and ASD was found. Two recent studies (Cass et al., 2008; Hunter et al., 2007) have also failed to find a difference in levels of peptides in the urine of autistic children as opposed to those without autism. In 2009, a review of the studies done on opioid-autism link did not find evidence to show that urinary peptide levels were correlated with gut permeability, which was supposedly to cause ASD (Mulloy et al., 2010).

Hopefully, in the near future, research will be able to explain why individuals with ASD lack pain sensitivity or possess a high tolerance of pain.

Definition of Pain

Pain has been defined as “a feeling triggered in the nervous system ... be it ... sharp or dull. It may come and go, or it may be constant. Pain is mediated by specific nerve fibers that carry the pain impulses to the brain where their conscious appreciation may be modified by many factors” (Disabled World, 2019, para.1-2). According to the American Psychiatric Association (1994, 2000), the term “a high threshold for pain” has been used when referring to pain sensitivity in the publication of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) Fourth Edition (DSM-IV) (APA, 1994) and its Text Revision (DSM-IV-TR) (APA, 2000). However, in the earlier DSM-III (APA, 1987), the term used was “ignoring of pain.” Individuals with ASD are often mistakenly to have reduced pain sensitivity: e.g., not feeling pain as intensely as others (Gillberg, 1988), and being indifferent to pain (Wing, 1996). It is not true that individuals with ASD are insensitive to pain. Their experience of feeling pain is not the same as typical people without ASD. Hence, there is a need to have a different approach to measure pain in such people.

Measuring Pain: Why and How?

Measuring the pain level can help in diagnosing a problem (e.g., arthritis or cancer) (Disabled World, 2019) as well as self-inflicted pain in non-suicidal self-injury (Higgins, 2015). However, there are also reported cases of individuals who do not feel pain at all. Known as congenital analgesia, this congenital insensitivity to pain (CIP) is a rare condition in which an individual is unable to feel physical pain (Linton, 2005). However, it does not come under the hereditary sensory and autonomic neuropathy (HSAN) or hereditary sensory neuropathy (HSN) group of disorders. As feeling for physical pain is vital for survival, the CIP is considered an extremely dangerous condition (Linton, 2005). Often individuals with CIP die during the childhood period due to injuries or sickness that have gone unnoticed (Linton, 2005; Hellier, 2016).

Figure 1. Pain Scale Chart
(Courtesy of The Disabled World, 2019)

However, there is more than just the varying degree of pain experienced by an individual. There are also different types of pain and Figure 2 shows a simplified classification of pain categories:

- (i) **Physiological pain (physialgia):** It is related to bodily functions, e.g., an individual with cerebral palsy may experience pain caused by spasticity due to mild feeling of tight muscles or it can be severe enough to cause painful spasms of the extremities, usually the legs. Another example is pain from a fractured leg or arm that has to be put in a cast.
- (ii) **Psychological pain (psychalgia):** It refers to physical pain caused, increased, or prolonged by mental (e.g., stress), emotional (e.g., anxiety and frustration), or behavioral factors, e.g., headache, backache and stomach ache. A severe headache disorder is classified under neurological pain.
- (iii) **Neurological pain (neuralgia):** It originated in the nervous system: 1) central nervous system; and 2) peripheral nervous system, which is further divided into three others: somatic, autonomic and enteric nervous sub-systems. An example is migraine, whose associated symptoms include nausea, vomiting and an aura of sensory disturbances (e.g., sensitivity to light, sound or smell), is often followed by a severe headache affecting one side of the head, lasting between two to 72 hours. It can be worsened by physical activity.

Figure 2. A Model of Pain Classification

There are also three other sub-categories of pain that exist between the three categories of pain. The first sub-category is the phantom pain – a form of neuropathic pain. Its sensation comes from an amputated limb or organ that an individual no longer receives its physical signals. The phantom pain (also known as the Phantom Limb Syndrome) is an experience that has been universally reported by amputees and quadriplegics. This form of pain falls between physialgia and neuralgia. The next sub-category is the somatoform pain characterized by symptoms suggesting a physical disorder, but for which no demonstrable organic findings or known physiological mechanisms can be found or seen. An example is the fibromyalgia – a medical condition characterized by chronic widespread pain and also a heightened pain response to pressure (Ngian, Guymer, & Littlejohn, 2011). This form of pain falls between physialgia and psychalgia. Finally, there is a third sub-category of pain which falls between neuralgia and psychalgia. Also known as neuropathic pain or somatosensory pain, it is caused by damage or dysfunction affecting both somatic and sensory nervous systems. This form of pain may be associated with abnormal sensations called dysesthesia or pain from normally non-painful sensory stimuli (allodynia). It may have continuous and/or episodic components (e.g., pain that resembles stabbings or electric shocks). Common qualities include burning or coldness, “pins and needles” sensations, numbness and itching. It is this form of pain that individuals with ASD often complain they are suffering or experiencing. Elwin et al. (2012) reviewed several research studies and autobiographies published on hyper- and hypo-sensitivity in individuals with ASD and found that this somatosensory pain could be indistinctly experienced by individuals with ASD, who often possess a very high pain threshold (Allely, 2013) or as reported by Gerland (1997) about an adult with ASD saying “... I had a very high pain threshold, and even when I did hurt I never showed what I felt. I did not know what you should do” (p.92). This is a good example of pain hyposensitivity – a form of pain that “was experienced as a result of sensory abnormalities not specifically related to what would typically be defined as a painful event (e.g., bodily injury). In one case reviewed by Elwin et al. (2012), an individual with ASD “reported feeling excruciating pain racking through her head in response to a fog horn” (cited in Allely, 2013, p.4). This is an example of pain hypersensitivity due to sensory overloading caused by sound (auditory processing).

Each of the categories and sub-categories of pain can be further divided into three types based on the duration of pain:

- (i) Acute pain: This form of pain comes and goes quickly, and it can be severe, too, though lasting a relatively short while. Often acute pain serves as a warning sign of a disease or a threat to the body.
- (ii) Intermittent pain: There is a difference between intermittent and episodic pain. The former is stopping and starting at intervals, not steady or constant, while latter is relating to an episode, consisting of a series of separate events occurring occasionally and at irregular intervals; and
- (iii) Chronic pain: This form of pain persists a longer time and is often associated with a specific type of injury or disease. Often high-intensity chronic pain impairs or reduces an individual's ability to perform attention-demanding tasks. One of the hardest things about chronic pain is that only the sufferer knows how bad the pain feels. There are no tests that reveal how much one is suffering. There are always no outward signs showing how much an individual is in pain.

Conclusion

For pain relief specialists and therapists offering pain management programs to help clients reduce pain sensitivity or correct their perception of pain, it is also important to pay a very special attention to those who are autistic because of three important factors already mentioned: Factor 1 – a wide range of pain sensitivity (from hypo-sensitivity to hyper-sensitivity); Factor 2 – varying forms of pain; and Factor 3 – a varying duration of pain. Figure 3 shows a radar chart on a client's pain sensitivity based on clinical observation and measurement.

Figure 3. An example of a Radar Chart on Pain Sensitivity

In fact, clinical ASD experience among the pain relief practitioners is of utmost importance. Extensive experience and good knowledge of atypical development in people with ASD would also be essential.

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